

Building Scalable Nature-Use Indicators for Thriving Cities: Modelling demand for park quality using mobile phone app data

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GISRUK 2026

Summary

Thriving cities agendas increasingly seek indicators that are scalable and repeatable, yet measurement of everyday human-nature interactions remains constrained by traditional methods. Using a multi-city UK case study (486 parks across Birmingham, Glasgow, Edinburgh, Manchester and Bristol), we combine mobile phone app data with objective park quality metrics to derive mobile visitor-days as a proxy for demand. Negative Binomial models show park quality explains substantial variation in visitation, supporting scalable nature-use indicators. The goal is to provide a foundation that can be repeated at scale and linked to objective, replicable spatial metrics.

KEYWORDS: Urban parks; Park quality; Mobile phone app data; Ecosystem service; Thriving city

1. Introduction

Thriving cities agendas, exemplified by the C40 Thriving Cities Initiative^{***} and UN-Habitat programmes^{†††}, focus on creating equitable, sustainable, and resilient urban environments. In this context, cities increasingly seek to understand whether they are becoming places where people can thrive, while delivering social priorities within environmental limits (Fanning & Raworth, 2025). Achieving this requires indicators that are not only conceptually meaningful, but also scalable, repeatable, and suitable to monitor change over time. Yet for many everyday urban experiences, especially those shaped by routine behaviour rather than formal services, measurement remains constrained by the limited coverage, cost, and infrequency of surveys, audits, and manual counts (Monz et al., 2019, Heikinheimo et al., 2020, Wood et al., 2013, Meyer et al., 2015, Winder et al., 2025). One such measurement challenge concerns everyday human-nature interactions. Urban parks and public gardens support physical activity, mental wellbeing and social connection (Giles-Corti et al., 2005; Astell-Burt et al., 2014; White et al., 2019), but access alone is an incomplete story: parks differ

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*** <https://www.c40.org/what-we-do/raising-climate-ambition/inclusive-thriving-cities/thriving-cities/>

††† <https://unhabitat.org/programme/inclusive-communities-thriving-cities>

in amenities, facilities, attractions, accessibility and biodiversity, and these features shape how places are used (van Dillen et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2021; Knobel et al., 2019). At the same time, less is known about whether objectively ‘better’ parks are visited more, and which dimensions of quality matter most at scale, because comparable visitation data are rarely available across hundreds of sites and multiple cities.

This work addresses that gap by demonstrating how mobile phone app data can be combined with objective geospatial measures of park quality to produce scalable nature-use indicators. Using a multi-city UK case study, we derive park-level mobile visitor-days as a proxy for demand and link this to multidimensional indicators of park quality. We focus on what such data can tell us, while showing a transparent workflow for bias adjustment and inference that supports comparisons across socio-economic contexts. The goal is not to replace qualitative insight into motivations or experience, but to provide a repeatable foundation that can inform indicator design for thriving cities agendas.

2. Study context and data

2.1 Study context: parks in five UK cities

We focus on parks and public gardens as defined in Ordnance Survey’s Open Greenspace (2021)^{†††}, across five major UK cities: Birmingham, Glasgow, Edinburgh, Manchester, and Bristol. Within these cities, we include all sites covered by the objective park quality audit of Hepburn et al. (2025). This yields 486 parks in total, providing a large, multi-city testbed for linking park quality (supply) with observed park use (demand).

Figure 1 Public parks in five cities

Table 1 Summary of parks across the study area

City	Population in 2021	Number of parks	Total park area (km ²)	Median park area (km ²)
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^{†††} Ordnance Survey, 2021. Open Greenspace dataset [Dataset] © Crown copyright and/or database rights 2021. OS (Research Licence).

Birmingham	1,069,690	125	27.30	0.03
Bristol	457,431	96	12.64	0.03
Edinburgh	526,470	91	13.10	0.03
Glasgow	635,130	103	17.99	0.02
Manchester	498,661	71	8.29	0.02

2.2 Mobile phone application data (park demand)

Park demand is estimated using a multi-app smartphone location dataset from Huq Industries (huq.io). The dataset provides timestamped location points collected passively through a wide range of partner apps, leveraging multiple positioning technologies (e.g., GPS, Bluetooth, cellular towers, Wi-Fi) to achieve higher spatial precision than more traditional mobile phone data sources (Wang et al., 2019; Vanky et al., 2017). The data are from mobile phone users aged 16 and older, collected on an informed consent basis, with personal identifiers replaced by non-reversible hashed IDs.

The analysis uses raw GPS point data rather than vendor-processed visit products to support transparent cleaning and consistent visit rules across cities. The study period spans 2021, with data contributed by 200+ partner apps across the five cities and substantial variation in volume by city.

Figure 2 Mobile phone app data in five cities

2.3 Objective park quality metrics (park supply)

We use objective quality indicators developed by Hepburn et al. (2025), organised into five health-promoting domains: amenities, facilities, attractions, accessibility, and biodiversity. These measures capture features such as cafés, toilets, sports facilities, public transport provision, bike paths, tree cover, and water features, and are computed both within park boundaries and within a 100 m buffer to capture nearby features that shape use.

Table 2 Descriptive summary of park quality attributes for model

Attribute group	Attribute name	Description
Park-level	Area	Park area (m ²)

Attribute group	Attribute name	Description
factors		
Amenities	Café	Cafes present within the park and 100 m catchment
	Toilet	Toilets present within the park and 100 m catchment
	Info	Information points present within the park
Facilities	Sports	Sports facility present within the park
Attractions	Public attractions	Public attractions present within the park
	Types of public attractions	Number of types of public attractions present within the park
Accessibility	Bike path	Maximum density (km/km ²) of bike paths within the park and 100 m catchment
	Public transport	Public transport features present within the park and 100 m catchment
	Types of public transport	Number of types of public transport features within the park and 100 m catchment
Biodiversity	Tree cover	Percentage of park area with tree cover
	Water feature	Presence of park area with standing (pond/fountain) or moving (river) water feature

Table 3 Descriptive stats of park quality attributes

Attribute group	Attribute name	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max	Levels (n, %)
Park-level factors	Area	163,201.08	577,378.17	29,760.09	81.33	8,684,764.53	—
Amenities	Toilet	0.27	0.73	0	0.0	6	—
	Café	0.64	1.85	0	0.0	18	—
	Info	0.01	0.09	0	0.0	1	—
Facilities	Sports	0.97	1.64	0	0.0	12	—
Attractions	Public attractions	1.64	2.36	1	0.0	15	—
	Types of public attractions	1.1	1.16	1	0.0	7	—
Accessibility	Bike path	0.54	1.35	0.0	0.0	8.64	—
	Public transport	5.76	7.41	4	0.0	76	—
	Types of public transport	0.88	0.47	1	0.0	3	—
Biodiversity	Tree cover	40.97	25.42	39.74	0.0	100.0	—
Park-level factors	Water feature	—	—	—	—	—	1: 148 (41.5%), 0: 209 (58.5%)

2.4 Small-area context and supporting datasets

To support socio-demographic profiling and bias adjustment, we assign users to Lower Layer Super

Output Areas (LSOAs) in England and Datazones in Scotland, and link area deprivation using IMD and SIMD (using IMD 2020 and SIMD 2019, the closest releases to the 2021 study period). We use mid-2021 official population estimates to compare mobile sample distributions to adult population structure and derive weights. For home-area inference we use Verisk’s UKBuildings (residential or mixed-residential), and for GPS cleaning we draw on OS Open Roads and UK railways data to reduce contamination from motorised travel near park edges.

3. Method

3.1 Preprocessing mobile phone app data

To represent actual park activity, we apply two cleaning rules. First, because many parks are adjacent to urban roads and railways, we remove points likely to reflect motorised travel rather than park use. We obtain road and railway network data, exclude internal park roads, and buffer remaining roads/railways to identify potentially contaminated areas. Using a conservative cycling-speed threshold of 20 km/h and sensitivity checks, we find that the majority of high-speed points fall within 25 m of roads/railways; we therefore remove all points within a 25 m buffer of roads/railways. Second, we exclude users who record only a single GPS point within a park on a given day, as such points are not reliable evidence of a visit.

3.2 Estimating home locations of mobile phone app users

To enable socio-demographic comparisons while minimising re-identification risk, we estimate home areas using an established approach based on night-time activity heuristics.

We apply the same approach developed by Sinclair et al. (2023), which identify each user’s most frequent location during night-time activity (20:00-06:00), using only points with reported accuracy of ≤ 100 m. We then retain only points located within buildings classified as residential or mixed-residential in a high-resolution building-use dataset. The user’s home area is defined as the LSOA/Datazone where they are active on the greatest number of evenings during the study period; users active on only one evening are not assigned a home location due to low reliability.

3.3 Comparing representativeness and calculating mobile sample weights

We assess socio-demographic representativeness by comparing the distribution of mobile users by estimated home area with the official adult population (16+) across IMD/SIMD groups, using both quintile comparisons (Figure 3) and percentile-scale regression fits (Figure 4).

Figure 3 Fit of IMD/SIMD Quintile between mobile users and official adult population across five cities

Figure 4 Fit of IMD/SIMD Percentile between mobile users and official adult population across five cities

To correct remaining discrepancies, we construct a post-stratification weight at the city \times IMD/SIMD group level. The weight increases the contribution of under-represented groups (weight > 1) and reduces the influence of over-represented groups (weight < 1). The mobile sample weight is calculated as:

$$MSW_{group} = \frac{AP_{group}}{MP_{group}} \quad (1)$$

Where MSW_{group} is the mobile sample weight for a specific sociodemographic group in a given city. AP_{group} is the proportion of the adult population belonging to this group in the city. MP_{group} is the corresponding proportion of the mobile population in the city.

3.4 Modelling visitation using park quality data

We model the relationship between park demand and park quality by regressing annual aggregated mobile sample-weighted visitor-days on objective park quality attributes. Because the dependent variable is strongly right-skewed with substantial overdispersion, we use a Negative Binomial regression model with a log link. The model is specified as:

$$Y_i \sim \text{NegBin}(\mu_i, \alpha), \quad (2)$$

$$\log(\mu_i) = \beta_0 + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k X_{ik}, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Var}(Y_i) = \mu_i + \alpha \mu_i^2, \quad (4)$$

where Y_i denotes the annual number of mobile sample-weighted visitor days to park i , μ_i is its expected value, and α is an overdispersion parameter allowing the variance to exceed the mean. X_{ik} represents the k th park quality attribute, and β_k is the corresponding regression coefficient.

We estimate two specifications: (1) a fully adjusted basic model including all candidate predictors, and (2) an AIC-based backward-selection model to highlight the strongest and most stable predictors. Multicollinearity is assessed using VIF with all predictors below common thresholds.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Socio-demographic patterns of park visitors and visitor-days

Estimating users' home areas enables us to attach small-area socio-demographic profiles and examine

park use across deprivation groups. Across the five cities, mobile sample representativeness varies by city and deprivation group. Figure 5 shows the weights, where values above one indicate under-representation that requiring up-weighting and values below one indicate over-representation. Birmingham and Manchester have median weights above one, Edinburgh and Bristol below one, and Glasgow is closest to one with a relatively narrow interquartile range, suggesting comparatively good alignment between the mobile sample and the adult population.

Figure 5 Mobile sample weights distribution across five cities

After applying these weights, Figure 6 compares the distribution of weighted park visitors and weighted visitor-days across IMD/SIMD quintiles with adult population shares in each city. Patterns broadly follow population shares, but clear socio-economic gradients remain in some cities. For example, in Glasgow, visitors from the least deprived groups (SIMD 4 and 5) contribute a larger share of both weighted park visitors and visitor-days than expected from population shares, while SIMD 1 (most deprived group) contributes a smaller share; Bristol shows a similar tendency, with relatively lower use among IMD 1. As these measures are already weighted, these patterns are more plausibly interpreted as differences in park use behaviour rather than residual sample bias.

Figure 6 IMD/SIMD of visits by city compared to adult population

4.2 Linking park demand to multidimensional park quality

We model annual aggregated mobile sample-weighted visitor-days as a function of objective park quality attributes across five domains (amenities, facilities, attractions, accessibility, biodiversity), measured within parks and within a 100 m buffer.

The models show stable, relatively high explanatory power, with pseudo- R^2 around 0.65 in both the basic and backward stepwise specifications. The stepwise model achieves a slightly lower AIC while maintaining comparable fit, yielding a more parsimonious specification. Key coefficients remain directionally consistent across specifications, supporting robustness.

Table 4 Negative Binomial regression model results for park visitation and park quality attributes

Attribute group	Attribute name	Basic model	Backward stepwise
Park-level factors	Area	1.529e-07	1.626e-07
Amenities	Café	0.0763*	0.0816*
	Toilet	0.2141*	0.2103*
	Info	-1.6708*	-1.5803*
Facilities	Sports	0.1906***	0.1941***
Attractions	Public attractions	0.0276	—
	Types of public attractions	0.1150	0.1598**
Accessibility	Bike path	0.1264**	0.1271**
	Public transport	0.0504***	0.0510***
	Types of public transport	0.3523**	0.3446**

Attribute group	Attribute name	Basic model	Backward stepwise
Biodiversity	Tree cover	0.0107***	0.0107***
	Water feature	0.3269**	0.3298**
Pseudo R-squared		0.6550	0.6548
Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)		3120.7	3118.9
Log-Likelihood		-1547.3	-1547.5

Notes: p values denoted by asterisks: * = $p \leq 0.05$, ** = $p \leq 0.01$, *** = $p \leq 0.001$. Blank cells indicate predictor exclusion from the backward stepwise model.

Across both specifications, several attributes are consistently associated with higher visitation. Among amenities and facilities, cafés, toilets, and sports facilities show positive and statistically significant effects, highlighting the combined importance of social and active recreational functions. Accessibility also plays a key role: higher bike-path density, greater public transport provision, and a wider diversity of transport types are robust predictors of increased visitation. With respect to attractions, the number of public attractions is not a significant predictor and is removed in the stepwise model, whereas the diversity of attraction types becomes positively associated with visitation, suggesting variety may matter more than quantity. Biodiversity features remain important: higher tree cover and the presence of water features are both positively associated with visitation.

4.3 Discussion

Two interpretive points are worth emphasising. First, park size alone is not a strong predictor once multidimensional quality is included: the coefficient on area is positive but not statistically significant, consistent with the idea that access alone is an incomplete story. Second, the results demonstrate that a relatively small set of objectively measured features can explain a substantial share of variation in observed demand across hundreds of open-access sites, supporting the use of mobile visitor-days as a practical proxy for demand where routine administrative visitation data are unavailable. In a thriving cities context, this supports indicator development in complementary ways, such as nature-use intensity, equity of nature-use (e.g., deprivation gradients in use), and quality-demand leverage.

Taken together, these findings suggest that visits derived from mobile phone app data can serve as a useful proxy for park demand at spatial and temporal scales that are difficult to capture using traditional methods. However, mobile app data do not capture motivations, perceptions, or experiential quality directly. The value of the approach is therefore not to replace methods that explain why people visit, but to provide a scalable foundation that can be repeated over time and linked to objective, replicable spatial metrics. Although this analysis is limited to five UK cities, the combination of mobile visitation data and national-scale objective quality metrics provides a framework that could be applied at wider scale, including longitudinal monitoring and extension to other public and natural spaces.

5. Acknowledgements

This research was funded by ESRC's SDAI grant [ES/W012979/1].

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